

Social Media Marketing: Opportunities and Threats for Young Entrepreneurs in Pakistan

Atif Hassan*, Erum Fatima** and Dr. Rizwana Bashir***

* Assistant Professor, DHA Suffa University, Karachi

** Lecturer, DHA Suffa University, Karachi.

*** Assistant Professor, Bahria University, Karachi.

ABSTRACT: *The ambition of doing this research is to discover how the usage of social media marketing is helping young entrepreneurs in doing business activities with special reference to Pakistan. Many young entrepreneurs have taken advantage of their computer literacy and have started doing business through the web providing additional income to their families in such dire economic conditions. This research helped in identifying various opportunities that social media marketing has helped young entrepreneurs in expanding their business and to create awareness among deserving and potential entrepreneurs about social media options. This research study also focuses on the threats of using social media by the youth. The results showed that social media is the most popular tool among entrepreneurs as it is a safe and secure system for earning their livelihood.*

Keywords: Social Media Marketing,

INTRODUCTION:

The internet revolution has not only affected the way people use technology but it has immensely affected the way people used to do business around the globe. Social media marketing is one of the internet related technologies that have changed the business environment. Many people have taken advantage of this technology and have increased tremendously in terms of size and profit, whereas on the other hand, many companies have suffered a serious setback because of ignoring the effects of this newly born technology over their business. Gone are the days when business was done on the basis of face to face meetings only, nowadays most of the business are done solely on the basis of information and communications technologies such as teleconferencing, e-marketing, online ordering, e-commerce etc.

The article compares effectiveness of advertisement done on social media when compared to Google and shows the results in favor of social media because the social networking websites offer better targeting with keywords and demographic-specific ads. Social media uses the information it gathers from the profiles of the users but Google has very little information about the page visitor when compared to social media. Social media has knowledge about your likes, what causes do you support, which videos do you share and how often you make recommendations to your friends. Therefore, advertising done on Facebook and other such similar social networking sites are more results oriented and effective when compared to the Google network.

The main endeavor of this paper is to examine the role of social networking websites in the success of young entrepreneurs in Pakistan. The issue is very significant since young entrepreneurship development is part of ongoing national efforts to alleviate poverty in developing countries in relation to Millennium Development Goals (MDG's).

Sinhaal (2005) observed that less than 10% of the entrepreneurs in South Asia comprising Bangladesh, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka, are young men and women. However with the internet revolution, situation is transforming as women entrepreneurs of this region have started using social media networks such as Facebook, twitter and LinkedIn to start, run and make their business grow.

Nylander and Rudstrom (2011) found that with the help of these social networking sites, entrepreneurs connect with new people rather than reifying offline networks. Many entrepreneurs in Pakistan have made their profile pages, where they have given complete details of

their business and products. They have uploaded pictures of the product so as to make it easy for the customer to order. They regularly update any new arrivals or discounts they are offering and customer queries about price or delivery are regularly answered.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

The researcher made an extensive study for the literature on the problem under study. Literature was nice on the topic and the awareness about the topic is very encouraging among the youth.

With the advancement in internet usage and internet related technologies, the number of people adopting these technologies have increased many fold in recent years. This has not only changed the life style of the people but it has also changed the way business was done and had transformed the business environment throughout the world. Even a decade ago, more than 600 million people access internet by the end of 2002 and spent more than US \$1 trillion buying goods and services online around the world (Mansuwe, 2004).

According to the survey by Nielson Online (2011), by the end of December 2011, the number of internet users has reached to approximately 2,267,233,742 against total population of 6,930,055,154.

With the passage of time the number has grown many times, however, the growth and penetration of e-commerce in developing economies like Pakistan is still on the lower side. Under the national IT policy, the government of Pakistan has established seven "IT Universities" and one virtual university as a step to produce more qualified knowledge workers in conformity with the current needs of ICT age. In response to the government's policy, the internet penetration is growing in an exponential manner. From a humble start of 10,000 users in the year of 1998, the internet users had reached to 1.3 million in 2001 and to 7.5 million by the end of 2005 (Shahzada, 2006).

According to a news published on October 28, 2011 in The Express Tribune, Pakistani internet users have been on the rise at an accelerated pace, crossing the 20 million benchmark as a greater percentage accessing the internet via mobile phones, said Freedom on the Net in its 2011 annual report. The report cited International Telecommunications Union (ITU) and said that estimated users have been surging significantly on a monthly basis in Pakistan.

This high penetration of internet has not only gathered attention of businesses but it has also attracted consumers. They are turning

towards online shopping as it is considered hassle free and can be done at any time of the day. In developed countries like Japan and USA, e-commerce is at full swing whereas in developing countries like Pakistan and Bangladesh, the usage of e-commerce is still very low.

According to (Aljifri, 2003), the successful implementation of e-commerce in developing countries like Pakistan is subject to a variety of forces. One of these forces is the trust within the system itself. Issues such as cultural encroachment, technological dependence, economic issues and local regulations are the factors that contribute to the trust level on the system. To gain customer's trust and satisfaction in an online business is a daunting task as there is no face to face interaction among the buyer and the seller.

The term "electronic commerce" or "e-commerce" has no widely accepted definition¹ however, according to the UNCITRAL Model Law on E-Commerce, it comprises of the "Commercial activities using a data message generated, sent, received or stored by electronic, optical or similar means including, but not limited to, electronic data interchange (EDI), e-mail, telegram, telex or telecopy." E-commerce could vaguely be defined as doing business over the Internet. It comprises the advertising and searching, marketing, distributing and selling of goods and services which are delivered offline as well as products which can be delivered digitally, i.e. directly over the Internet, such as computer software, travel bookings, banking and insurance services. E-Commerce or Electronic Commerce covers the range of online business activities for products and services, both business to business and business to consumer, through the internet. Anita Rosen (2002)

Cha (2009) studied some of the surveys related to internet shopping and found out that more recent surveys, such as the Pew internet (2002) and Sky News (2002), indicated that women are more dominant than men when it comes to e-commerce. Focusing on expenditures online, women accounted for 58% of online shopping, whereas men were responsible for 42% between April 2004 and March 2005, according to comScore (Maguire 2006).

Cha (2009) has quoted the work of Girard, Korgaonka, and Silverblatt (2003) find that online shopping preferences depend on product types. Men are more likely to shop online for books; computers and other "utilitarian experience" goods (e.g., cell phones, televisions). Women instead shop online for hedonic experience goods, such as perfume and clothing.

Cha (2009) has also discussed the Market Watch Survey, which says Social media play increasingly important roles as a marketing platform. More and more retailer's use social media to target teens and young adults, and social networking site are a central venue in that trend (Market Watch 2008).

Although online shopping has grown rapidly in recent years, some internet users remain reluctant to purchase goods on the internet because they are skeptical of how much privacy and security they have in doing so (Aldridge, Forchst, and Pierson 1997; Wang, Yeh, and Jiang 2006). Others may hesitate to shop online because they would miss the social interaction or direct experience with products.

The role social media is playing in bringing change to the society and in creating awareness among the masses on any issue is influential. People think that if they want to spread news about something or want to have views of like-minded people on something in a cost effective manner than the use of social media is the first that comes to their mind. Facebook had around 500 million users across the globe in 2011. The opportunity for a small business to have access to this many people was a dream years ago but it is a reality today for entrepreneurs.

Social Media has affected everyone in the society as it is not used by the young generation, but the older generation is also benefitting from it to reconnect with old friends and family members, living abroad. Facebook is the most popular among all types of social media as it has both personal and professional usage. Unlike other e-commerce sites that tend to mitigate opportunities for social interaction during shopping, social networking sites enable users to interact with their friends. For example, Facebook added a shopping application that enables users to search for products they want to buy, and then share their opinions of those products with other Facebook members (Forbes 2007).

Although, E-commerce is very common and expanding rapidly, but most people in Pakistan doesn't understand what E-commerce is and how it works? This is one of the main reasons that many companies in Pakistan at current are not engaging in E-Commerce. Low level of understanding coupled with the unavailability of proper internet framework across the country has led many Pakistani firms to give low priority to e-commerce. Seyal and Awais (2010) found that in Pakistan 84% of organizations have internet accounts, whereas 64% of the organizations have claimed average to above adoption of e-commerce. This study shows that adoption of ecommerce in Pakistani firms is not very quick and this point has become an advantage for individual women entrepreneurs, as they are not facing very intense competition from well established firms. Therefore they are able to attract more customers and tap new markets, where e-commerce is understood.

Nicole B. Ellison (2007) said in his research that Facebook is a popular social networking site, it is found to interact with measures of psychological wellbeing, claiming it to be helping in giving satisfaction and person using Facebook feels his importance. According to him social capital is linked to a variety of positive social outcomes, it helps to maintain public health and reduces crimes rates and when this social capital declines it increased social disorders, civic activities declines and create miss understanding among community members. Social capital increase commitment to community through which we help others and can do those activities which help to reduce gap and differences between people for welfare of the society. Social networking keeps on changing which affect social capital, when a person moving from one place to another for any reason social capital decreased only through internet and these social networks we can keep in touch all the time. Because of Facebook, people feel that they have a number of good qualities through which they take positive attitude toward life.

In this article Chris Lecompte said that social websites are very effective to convince consumer about their products. He is in the favor of Facebook by saying this that many small businesses are jumping on it. Facebook main motive is to provide social networking not for doing business, it is a rapidly evolving service with new features and functions, but it also provide³ a good starting point to

¹ UNCTAD, Building Confidence: Electronic Commerce and Development, 2000.

get your small and non-profit organization into the 21st century of social networking.

By three ways Facebook proved to be helpful; research, implementation and measure. it is an excellent source of market, demographic and psychographic research. We can gather data just looking at people post, say and links. Facebook give us an opportunity to connect with younger and older generation. we can start small business by spend some time on reviewing videos and pictures posted which shows the interest of the person, start building a persona of that user as it relates to our organization then use the persona to user prospects and customers through this we can reached to those whom we don't know. The next step is to establish a good profile through which we can connect with friends, family, colleagues, partners, clients and others, for this we should keep our profile updated, keep checking our notifications and messages. Facebook informed us who a person on facebook is friends with, whether they are my friend or not, it is useful because it serve us a potential way to develop that connection now for this we should be genuine and build trust.

According to Libby Copeland's research Facebook makes ourselves feel lousy. After logging to Facebook and scrolling through others' attractive photos, accomplished bios and status updates we are easily convinced that everyone else was leading a perfect life but which is not true, it is the human habit of overestimating other's happiness is nothing new and we always want to be happy more than other people which is difficult. She is of the view that the sites have a special power to make us sadder and lonelier.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

- Questionnaires are used to collect data.
- Questionnaires will be filled by 540 young entrepreneurs from different cities of Pakistan including Karachi, Lahore and Islamabad.
- Questionnaires were emailed/messaged to the young entrepreneurs.

Sampling Frame:

There is no readily available sampling frame for choosing a statistical sample of young entrepreneurs in Pakistan, who are running businesses from their premises. Therefore a sample of 540 young entrepreneurs was considered to be enough for the study.

Sample Composition:

A large number of questionnaires were distributed to all available and reachable samples. Out of those first 540 responses were considered for the study due to limited time period. The questionnaires were distributed randomly to women entrepreneurs and they were requested to fill it timely.

Problems Faced During the Survey:

Some of the women entrepreneurs were reluctant to provide the details of their businesses; they thought that their details might be used by government for tax purposes and due to some social and cultural factors. They were ensured that their information will only be used for academic purposes and will be kept confidential.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS:

The analysis of the data collected through questionnaires showed that 69% of the respondents fall under the age category of 20-30 years where as 19% were above 30 years of age. The results reveal that survey capture young population.

Table 1: What is the age group of the respondents?

Below 20	70	13%
Between 20 and 30	360	68%
Between 30 and 40	80	15%
Between 40 and 50	20	4%
Above 50	0	0%

While the education analysis showed that 19% are under graduate, 43% of them are graduate, and 31% of the women entrepreneurs are master's degree holders. 98% of the women are doing business through social networking websites whereas the remaining 2% have their personal e-commerce website.

Table 2: What is the Qualification of the respondents?

Under Graduate	110	21%
Graduate	210	40%
Masters	180	34%
Ph.D	0	0%
Others	30	6%

Eighty percent (80%) of the respondents are of the view that doing business over the web has helped them increased in terms of profit. While in terms of percentage, 43% respondents said that their profit increased around 10%, 40% respondents said that their profit increased around 40%, and 17% are of the opinion that their profit increased around 60%. Fifty two (52%) percent of the entrepreneurs are doing business through the web only while the remaining 48% use other means as well. **Table 3: In terms of percentage how much profit has increased?**

Around 10%	230	43%
Around 40%	210	40%
More than 60%	90	17%

The analysis of the products, that the women entrepreneurs are offering, revealed that 43% of them are selling stitch or unstitch clothes, 15% of them are selling jewelry, hair and hijab clips.

Table 4: What type of product you are offering?

Clothing (Stitch/ Unstitch)	230	43%
Clothing (Hand Painted Dresses)	0	0%
Accessories (Jewelry /Clips/ Pins)	80	15%
Gift items (Candles/Jewelry box/ Flowers)	10	2%
Other	210	40%

Eighty percent (80%) of the respondents are of the view that doing business over the web has helped them increased in terms of profit. While in terms of percentage, 41% respondents said that their profit increased around 10%, 41% respondents said that their profit increased around 40%, and 19% are of the opinion that their profit increased around 60%. Fifty two (52%) percent of the entrepreneurs are doing business through the web only while the remaining 48% use other means as well.

Table 5: Has business over the web, helped you increase business in terms of profit?

Yes	430	81%
No	100	19%

The analysis further revealed that 49% are using cash on delivery as mode of payment, whereas credit card and cross cheques are also used by some of them.

Table 6: What is the mode of payment?

Cash on delivery	260	49%
Credit Card	40	8%
Cross Cheque	50	9%
Other	180	34%

Fifty six percent (57%) of the entrepreneurs deliver the products through courier service where as 32% of the entrepreneurs asked their consumers to pick their parcels from their place. However, all of them (young entrepreneurs) are of the view that their customers are satisfied with them and 93% of them enjoy doing business on the web.

Table 7: What is the mode of delivery?

Through courier service	300	57%
By company personnel	20	4%
Customers picked from your place	170	32%
Other	40	8%

Keeping in view today’s law and order situation of the country, 74% of the respondents think that people prefer online shopping as compared to traditional shopping.

Table 8: Keeping in mind, today’s situation do you think people prefer online shopping?

Yes	390	74%
No	140	26%

Sixty three percent (60%) of the entrepreneurs have marketed their business while the remaining 40% have never marketed their business. Eighty three percent (83%) of the respondents are of the view that their business has spread through word of mouth.

Table 9: Have you ever marketed your business?

Yes	320	60%
No	210	40%

The analysis of the responses on the question: “On average how many queries you receive in a month?” reveal that 17% receive below 5, 25% receive between 5-10 queries, where as 19% receive 10 to 15 queries and the remaining 40% receive above 15 queries in a month.

Table 10: On average how many queries you receive in a month?

Below 5	90	17%
Between 5 to 10	130	25%
Between 10 to 15	100	19%
Between 15 to 20	80	15%
Above 20	130	25%

Twenty six percent (25%) of the respondents believe that below 20% queries turn into order, 42% believe that between 20% to 40% queries turn into order while the remaining 34% believe that above 40% queries turn into order.

Table 11: On average how many queries turn into orders?

Below 20%	130	25%
Between 20% to 40%	220	42%
Between 40% to 60%	110	21%
Above 60%	70	13%

If the queries don't turn into order, the possible reasons according to 33% of women entrepreneurs is low understanding of e-commerce methods, 19% think high price and 19% think that better competitors are available while the remaining 20% think it is due to other reasons.

Table 12: If they don't turn into order, in your view what might be the possible reasons?

High price	100	19%
Differentiated products	50	9%
Better competitor	90	17%
Low understanding of E-commerce methods	170	32%
Other	120	23%

The overall analysis reveals that the youth is doing well both in terms of increase in profits and business. The one important aspect that was reveal from this study was that there is a very low percentage of young people in Pakistan who are using twitter, LinkedIn or e-commerce store website for their business.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION:

Electronic commerce is growing rapidly all over the globe and Pakistan is no exception. The advantages and cost savings offered from dealing on the internet, especially in business-to-business and business to consumer transactions have caused e-commerce to develop very fast. The Web is creating new employment opportunities for skilled IT young workers in technology firms as well as at home where, through teleworking, they have the possibility to work as home-based employees or home-based freelance consultants. Asian youth producers and distributors can benefit from substantial cost efficiencies and networking opportunities. Young entrepreneurs need to gear themselves to exploit the potential of e-commerce, and thus be a part of the global production system.

After going through a huge amount of literature and the results gathered from questionnaires, I have found out that most of the Pakistani young entrepreneurs are using facebook business page to conduct their business. The reason for using facebook being its ease of use; signing up, creating and maintaining personal and business profile, a large number of global users who can easily access your page.

Another important factor of using facebook is that whenever you update any information or picture of your product. It will be shown on the wall of all the people who are added as your friends. Special customers can be tagged in post or pictures to make sure they have a look at your stuff, but you don't need to send personal invitations

every time. You can also ask your existing clients and friends to help grow your business by asking their friends to join your page who might in future turn out to be a loyal customer.

Rehman.K, Rehman.I, Ashfaq.M and Ansari.S. (2011) conducted a study to cater the attitudes of Pakistani Population towards online shopping. The results divulge that majority of the subjects are already using online technologies for shopping and they prefer to shop online. Various attitudes of the consumers toward online purchasing are catered in the study which reveals that shopping online are easy, comfortable and better than real time shopping due to various reason. The listed reason subject provides are prices, Convenience, and recommendation by someone.

To further help the business community and the youth in particular, the government should back such business by providing them loan facility and by providing the secure payment system. This will not only help these women entrepreneurs in running their businesses smoothly but in return it will also help in improving the social status of families.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The reason for doing this research is:

In Pakistan, it is very difficult for young people to go out for earning even in educated families and urban areas.

Many young people are sole bread and butter earners for their families

Young graduates have better entrepreneurial abilities as compared to men provided they are given support and chance to prove their entrepreneurial abilities.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

Due to time and budget constraints, small sample size is used and samples from few cities such as Karachi are collected only.

This study is based on a review of key literature and primary data collected through questionnaires and face to face interviews with young entrepreneurs. Personal experience and observation also helped in collecting valuable information. Since conducting business through web without registering yourself as a proper company is a new phenomenon, therefore not enough data on total number of young entrepreneurs, amount of capital invested and turnover rate was available.

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